

ENHANCING SPEAKING SKILLS IN NON-PHILOLOGICAL STUDENTS
IS A CRITICAL ASPECT OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: Teaching English to non-philological students can be a challenging task, especially when it comes to improving their speaking skills. However, with the right methods and strategies in place, educators can effectively help these students become more confident and proficient speakers of the English language.

Keywords: competence, pronunciation, tools, critical thinking, motivation, skills.

One of the key methods for improving speaking skills in non-philological students is through regular and structured practice. This can involve activities such as role-playing, group discussions, and debates, which allow students to actively engage in speaking English in a supportive and interactive environment. By consistently practicing their speaking skills, students can gradually build their confidence and fluency in expressing themselves in English.

Another important method is to provide students with ample opportunities for real-life communication in English. This can include organizing language exchange programs, inviting native speakers to the classroom, or encouraging students to participate in English-language events and activities outside of school. By immersing students in authentic English-speaking environments, they are able to apply their language skills in practical and meaningful ways, which can significantly enhance their speaking abilities.

In addition, incorporating technology into the classroom can also be a valuable tool for improving speaking skills. Online resources, language learning apps, and virtual communication platforms can provide students with additional practice opportunities, feedback, and access to a wider range of English-speaking contexts. By integrating technology into language learning, educators can create a more dynamic and interactive learning experience for non-philological students.

Overall, by employing a combination of regular practice, real-life communication opportunities, and technology-enhanced learning, educators can effectively enhance the speaking skills of non-philological students and help them become more confident and proficient English speakers. With dedication, creativity, and a student-centered approach, educators can empower non-philological students to reach their full potential in speaking the English language.

Furthermore, creating a supportive and inclusive classroom environment is essential for helping non-philological students improve their speaking skills. Teachers should encourage a positive and respectful atmosphere where students feel comfortable expressing themselves and making mistakes. By fostering a safe space for communication, students are more likely to take risks and actively participate in speaking activities, leading to greater progress in their language development.

Additionally, incorporating a variety of speaking tasks and topics into lessons can help students expand their vocabulary and improve their fluency. Teachers can design activities that encourage students to talk about a wide range of subjects, from everyday activities to current events, to provide them with the opportunity to practice using different language structures and expressions. By diversifying the speaking tasks, educators can keep students engaged and motivated to continue developing their communication skills.

Lastly, integrating cultural elements into language learning can also enhance non-philological students' speaking abilities. Exploring the cultural aspects of the

English language through literature, music, films, and traditions can deepen students' understanding of the language and help them connect more personally to the material. By incorporating cultural content into lessons, teachers can make the language learning experience more meaningful and enjoyable for students, leading to a more holistic development of their speaking skills.

Stable combinations, stable phrases, and idioms occupy a large place in the student's language treasury, while making the speech meaningful and attractive, it increases the student's linguistic wealth. A student who does not speak fluently, even when he has mastered the lesson well, he is tired in his oral response, which does not show that the student has been well prepared for the lesson. Such students should be forced to communicate a lot in a foreign language. In particular, memorizing events and stories related to a foreign language, as well as poems, texts, dialogues and monologues, also gives good results. It is worth saying that in order to improve students' speech, in addition, in order to acquire oral and written communication skills and qualifications, it is recommended to participate in various conferences, give speeches in a foreign language, and give lectures.

Taking into account all the stages and directions of working with the stated and listed video data, types of reviews, different educational goals, the specificity of foreign language science, we can offer a sequence of stages. We suggest presenting them as algorithms for working with video materials and using them in foreign language teaching.

CONCLUSION

In short, in the process of organizing foreign language teaching, in the analysis of the problem of the image of the external world in the human psychological imagination and its reflection in the language, it is one of the most urgent problems to check their language and speech reserves, the memory of the units gathered in them, and the factors of this in teaching foreign language learners to speak a foreign language. one is counted. These problems make it necessary to

apply language and speech units in an associative direction in linguistics and foreign language teaching.

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